

Physicochemical Studies on Thorium Soaps in Solid State

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The thermal decomposition of thorium soaps is kinetically of zero order and the energy of activation for the decomposition process lies in the range of 6-11 kcal mol⁻¹. Infrared spectral data indicate that the fatty acids exist with dimeric structure through hydrogen bonding between the carboxyl groups of acid molecules whereas the metal soaps have an ionic character. The X-ray diffraction studies of these soaps revealed that thorium soaps have double layer structure with molecular axes slightly inclined to the basal plane.

MANY studies are available in recent literature on the alkali, alkaline earth and transition metal soaps, but comparatively less work has been reported¹⁻⁴ on rare earth metal soaps, although these soaps are being widely used in various industries.

The present work deals with the thermal, infrared and X-ray diffraction measurements of thorium soaps and has been initiated with a view to obtain structural informations in solid state.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and were purified by standard methods. Thorium soaps (caprate and laurate) were prepared by the direct metathesis of an aqueous solution of thorium nitrate with a hot solution of the corresponding sodium soap. The precipitated soap was filtered and washed first with distilled water and finally with alcohol. The metal soaps were first dried in an air-oven and finally under reduced pressure and further purified by recrystallisation. Melting points of thorium soaps were found to be caprate, 112.0 and laurate, 118.0°. The purity of the soaps was checked by elemental analysis and by determining the metal content of the soaps. The results of analysis were found in close agreement with the theoretically calculated values.

The thermogravimetric analysis of thorium soaps was carried out at a constant heating rate in a Mettler TG50 thermobalance by maintaining similar conditions throughout the investigations. The infrared absorption spectra (KBr) of the soaps were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 grating spectrophotometer in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹. The X-ray diffraction patterns for the thorium soaps were obtained with Philips PW 1730 diffractometer using Cu-K_α radiations filtered by a nickel foil over the range of diffractions angle, 2θ=6-65°, where θ is the Bragg angle.

Results and Discussion

Thermal analysis: The results of thermogravimetric analysis of the thorium soaps are recorded in Fig. 1. It is found that the final residue is almost equal to the theoretically calculated weight of thorium oxide from the molecular formula of the

Fig. 1. Thermograms of thorium soaps; loss in weight vs time: (O) caprate, and (●) laurate.

corresponding soap. A white crystalline powder is found condensed at the cold part of the tube surrounding the sample and it identified as caprone (b.p. 223°) and laurone (m.p. 69°) in case of caprate and laurate, respectively.

where, R is C₉H₁₉ or C₁₁H₂₃ for caprate and laurate, respectively.

The energy of activation for the decomposition reaction has been obtained from the slope of the

plots of Freeman and Carroll's⁵ equation (Fig. 2) and Coats and Redfern's⁶ equation (Fig. 3) and the values are found to be 9.2 and 5.5 kcal mol⁻¹ for caprate and 9.2 and 11.4 kcal mol⁻¹ for laurate from the above equations, respectively. The decomposition reaction is found kinetically of zero order.

Fig. 2. Freeman-Carroll type plots of thorium soaps: (○) caprate, and (●) laurate.

Fig. 3. Coats-Redfern type plots of thorium soaps: (○) caprate, and (●) laurate.

Infrared spectra: The wave numbers of some important absorption bands in the infrared absorption spectra of thorium soaps (caprate and laurate) are assigned and compared with those of the corresponding fatty acid. The absorption maxima in the spectra of fatty acids near 2660–2650, 1700–1680, 1470 and 950–930 cm⁻¹ are associated with the

localised carboxyl group of the acid molecule in the dimeric form and confirm the presence of hydrogen bonds between two molecules of fatty acids. The complete disappearance of the carbonyl frequency near 1700 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of thorium soaps indicates that there is a complete resonance between the two C=O bonds of the carboxylic groups of the soap molecule and two C–O bonds become identical with their force constants assuming an intermediate value between those of the normal double and single bonds. The appearance of two absorption bands corresponding to symmetric and antisymmetric stretching vibrations of carboxylate ion near 1460–1455 and 1550–1530 cm⁻¹, respectively, in the spectra of thorium soaps instead of one band of carbonyl frequency near 1700 cm⁻¹ confirms the ionic nature of these soaps.

The results show that the fatty acids exist with dimeric structure through hydrogen bonding between carbonyl groups of the two acid molecules whereas thorium soaps are ionic in nature and metal-to-oxygen bonds in these soaps have ionic character. The assigned frequencies are in agreement with the results of other workers^{7–9}.

X-Ray diffraction: Generally, the metal soaps do not give large crystals sufficient for a detailed single crystal examination, so the X-ray diffraction patterns (Figs. 4 and 5) of thorium soaps have been investigated to characterise the structure of these soaps.

A large number of intense peaks arising from the diffraction of X-rays by planes of thorium ions (known as basal planes) have been observed over the range 6–65° of the diffraction angle in the diffraction patterns of thorium soaps. The interplanar spacings (*d*) have been calculated from the positions of intense peaks using Bragg relationship, $n\lambda = 2d \sin \theta$, where λ is the wavelength of radiation. The calculated spacings together with the relative intensities with respect to the most intense peaks are recorded (Tables 1 and 2).

The appearance of the diffractions upto 15th order in the diffraction patterns of thorium soaps confirms good crystallinity for these soaps. The average planar distance, i.e. the long spacings for thorium caprate and laurate are 28.7 and 33.9 Å, respectively. The difference in the observed values of long spacings for thorium laurate and caprate is 5.2 Å which corresponds to double the length of additional methylene (–CH₂–) groups in the fatty acid radical constituent of the soap molecules. The values of the long spacings for these soaps are approximately equal to double the length of the fatty acid radical of the soap molecule. It is, therefore, suggested that the zigzag chains of fatty acid radicals extended straight forward in these soap molecules.

The observed values of the long spacings for laurate (33.9 Å) and caprate (28.7 Å) of thorium are smaller than the calculated dimensions of laurate

Fig. 4. X-Ray diffraction pattern of thorium caprate.

Fig. 5. X-Ray diffraction pattern of thorium laurate.

TABLE 1—X-RAY DIFFRACTION ANALYSIS OF THORIUM CAPRATE

Sl. no.	2θ	θ	$\sin \theta$	$\frac{\lambda}{2 \sin \theta}$	d^*	n	I/I_0
1.	6.20	3.10	0.054 1	14.251	28.592	2	0.7
2.	9.30	4.65	0.081 0	9.518	28.554	3	0.7
3.	12.40	6.20	0.108 0	7.138	28.552	4	0.3
4.	15.40	7.70	0.134 0	5.763	28.765	5	0.3
5.	18.50	9.25	0.160 7	4.797	28.782	6	0.2
6.	22.00	11.00	0.190 8	4.040	28.286	7	0.3
7.	24.90	12.45	0.215 5	3.577	28.616	8	0.4
8.	27.80	13.90	0.240 2	3.209	28.881	9	0.3
9.	31.10	15.55	0.267 9	2.877	28.770	10	0.3
10.	34.00	17.00	0.292 4	2.636	28.996	11	0.3
11.	37.50	18.75	0.321 8	2.399	28.788	12	0.2
12.	47.00	23.50	0.390 7	1.981	28.965	15	0.3

* Average value of $d=28.704 \text{ \AA}$.

TABLE 2—X-RAY DIFFRACTION ANALYSIS OF THORIUM LAURATE

Sl. no.	2θ	θ	$\sin \theta$	$\frac{\lambda}{2 \sin \theta}$	d^*	n	I/I_0
1.	5.20	2.60	0.045 4	16.982	33.964	2	0.9
2.	7.80	3.90	0.068 0	11.338	34.014	3	0.9
3.	10.40	5.20	0.090 6	8.509	34.036	4	0.8
4.	13.10	6.55	0.114 0	6.763	33.815	5	0.4
5.	15.70	7.85	0.136 5	5.648	33.888	6	0.4
6.	18.30	9.15	0.159 0	4.849	33.943	7	0.2
7.	20.90	10.45	0.181 3	4.252	34.016	8	0.6
8.	23.50	11.75	0.203 6	3.786	34.074	9	0.4
9.	26.40	13.20	0.228 4	3.375	33.750	10	0.2
10.	29.40	14.70	0.253 8	3.037	33.416	11	0.3
11.	31.50	15.75	0.271 3	2.841	34.092	12	0.2
12.	37.00	18.50	0.317 3	2.249	34.006	14	0.2

* Average value of $d=33.917 \text{ \AA}$.

(37.0 \AA) and caprate (32.0 \AA) ions from Pauling's values of atomic radii and bond angles, and this suggests that the molecular axes of these soaps are somewhat inclined to the basal planes. The metal ions fit into spaces between oxygen atoms of the ionised carboxyl group without a large strain of the bonds. The values of long spacings for thorium soaps show that the angle of inclination of

molecular axis of the soap to the basal plane increases slightly with the decrease in the number of carbon atoms in the fatty acid radical constituent of the soap molecules. A number of the diffraction peaks in the intermediate range of the diffraction angles are also observed in the diffraction patterns of thorium soaps and these are attributed to the diffraction of X-rays by planes of

much smaller separation than the basal planes. The calculated spacings from these peaks correspond to the shorter side spacings, *i.e.* the lateral distances between one soap molecules and the next in a layer. It is observed that the long spacings are fairly intense while the short spacing peaks are relatively weak. On the basis of long and short spacings, it is proposed that the metal ions in thorium soaps are arranged in a parallel plane, *i.e.* a basal plane equally spaced in the soap crystal with fully extended zigzag chains of fatty acid radicals on both sides of each basal plane and the thorium soaps have double layer structure as proposed by Vold and Hattiangdi¹⁰.

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